

The Effect of Micro and Macro Brand Ambassador Related To Soft and Hard Selling Language on Purchase Decision of Piero Shoes in Jakarta, Indonesia

Tirta Mandira Hudhi¹, Nila Armelia Windasari³

^{1,2} Master of Business Administration, School of Business & Management, Bandung Institute of Technology

ABSTRACT: The local shoe industry in Indonesia is growing, one of the local shoe brands that is well known is PIERO, which has been established since 1999. Having experienced its peak in the early 2000s, many efforts are being made by Piero to maintain its existence. The development of the digital world, especially the social media sector which eventually became social commerce, made Piero think about whether they should choose brand ambassadors and calculate the budget to collaborate with the right brand ambassador. Moreover, there are two kinds of digital brand ambassadors: micro and macro influencers. This issue ultimately becomes a problem that must be answered immediately, because PIERO's competitors have begun to move rapidly on social media with their brand ambassadors. The purpose of this research is to identify the effect between micro and macro brand ambassadors related to soft or hard language with brand trust, purchasing decision, brand image on Piero shoes. This research is using quantitative design. To conduct the study, the authors recruited 339 participants from an online social media then randomly assigned to one of four conditions: micro influencer with high selling language, micro influencer with low selling language, macro influencer with high selling language, and macro influencer with low selling language. They were then asked to view an Instagram post by the assigned influencer and fulfill the questionnaire. Based on the result of research analysis using spss through multi anova analysis, the author conclude that : Micro brand ambassador with soft selling language is more effective at brand trust and purchase decision, meanwhile Macro brand ambassador with hard selling language is more effective to represent a good brand image to the customer.

KEYWORDS: Brand ambassador, Micro Influencer, Macro Influencer, Marketing, Purchasing Decision.

INTRODUCTION

The global footwear market size was valued at \$409.5 billion in 2022, and is projected to reach \$725.1 billion by 2032, growing at a CAGR (Compound Annual Growth Rate) of 5.9% from 2023 to 2032 [1]. The Footwear Market is segmented on the basis of type, material, end users, distribution channel, and region. By type, the footwear Market is classified into athletic and non-athletic. Depending on the material, the market is categorized into leather and non-leather. By end users, it is categorized into men, women, and children. Depending on the distribution channel, the market is categorized into E-Commerce and offline channel. By region, the market is analyzed in North America, Europe, Asia Pacific, and LAMEA [1])

There are a number of large multinational companies within the global footwear industry, with sportswear brands well represented, one of the most well known being Nike. In 2021, Nike led its main direct competitors of Adidas and Puma with footwear segment revenues of approximately 28 billion U.S. dollars worldwide. In 2021/22, TJX Cos was the leading apparel and footwear retailing company in the world with revenues of 48.6 billion U.S. dollars. In regards to specialist footwear companies, Skechers posted the largest revenue worldwide at 5.9 billion euros in 2021. [2]

Meanwhile, The domestic footwear industry in Indonesia is quite vibrant. Indonesia was able to place itself in fourth position as the world's largest footwear producer, under China, India and Vietnam with a share of total world production of 6.3 percent.[3]. Referring to the 2019 World Foot-wear Yearbook report, Indonesia is the fourth largest footwear production center in the world with a total production of 1,271 million pairs of footwear. Indonesia is also the third largest exporter of footwear products in the world, with a total of 406 million pairs of footwear. [3]. "Unlike Vietnam, Indonesia together with China and India, apart from being the biggest exporters of footwear, these three countries are also the biggest consumers. So far, the most exported footwear from Indonesia is sports shoes," said Director General of the Chemical, Pharmaceutical and Textile Industry (IKFT) of the Ministry of Industry, Muhammad Khayam. [3]

The local shoe industry in Indonesia is also growing, one of the local shoe brands what is well known is PIERO, which has been established since 1999. Having experienced its peak in the early 2000s, many efforts are being made by Piero to maintain its day, and are sold at prices ranging from IDR 350,000 – IDR 600,000. After reaching the hardest point in 2018, Piero experienced 12-15% growth in 2019. Piero sells their products through retail stores spread across Indonesia, and also through the digital sector where 40% comes from Instagram social media.

BUSINESS ISSUE

During the COVID-19 pandemic era, everything changed, and Piero had to adapt to those changes. Piero observed the behaviors, habits, and preferences of young people during that time. The quickest response the company received was that the digital and internet space saw a significant increase in engagement. Consequently, their primary strategy and priority became to enhance digital marketing with a focus on achieving awareness and sales goals. The selection of social programs was also important because every segment of society experienced the negative ripple effects of the COVID-19 pandemic.

The development of the digital world, especially the social media sector which eventually became social commerce, made Piero think about whether they should choose brand ambassadors and calculate the budget to collaborate with the right brand ambassador. Moreover, there are two kinds of digital brand ambassadors : micro and macro influencers. PIERO should choose one of them that is suitable to their budget. This issue ultimately becomes a problem that must be answered immediately, because PIERO's competitors have begun to move rapidly on social media with their brand ambassadors.

LITERATURE REVIEW

1. Brand Ambassadors

A brand ambassador is someone who has a passion for a brand, wants to introduce and provide information about the brand. The use of brand ambassadors is carried out by companies to influence or encourage consumers to use these products. The use of brand ambassadors usually uses well-known celebrities. [4] Because of research on Social Media Revolution, Qualman [5] showed data that 78% of people trust other people's recommendations more than ads. One of the most effective Brand ambassadors in digital platforms is Influencer. [6]. Influencer marketing is a collaboration between popular social-media users and brands to promote brands' products or services. These partnerships have been going on informally since the dawn of social media. By 2009, they were sufficiently commonplace for the US Federal Trade Commission to step in and regulate them through the so-called Mommy Blogger law. (China, India, and the United Kingdom have introduced similar regulations.) [6].

In 2022, the influencer industry reached \$16.4 billion. More than 75% of brands have a dedicated budget for influencer marketing, from Coca Cola's #ThisOnesFor campaign in collaboration with fashion and travel influencers, to Dior's award-winning 67 Shades campaign in which the brand partnered with diverse influencers to promote its Forever Foundation product line. 1% increase in influencer marketing spend led to an increase in engagement of 0.46%, suggesting that the strategy can in fact yield positive ROI. [7] Influencers come in four different sizes—nano, micro, macro, and mega—depending on how many followers they have. [8] Nano influencers have fewer than 10,000 followers, Micro influencers have from 50,000 to 100,000, Macro influencers have more than 500,000 and Mega influencers breathe rarified air: they have over one million followers [8]

When choosing an influencer, the important points for brands are; to have the image of the trustworthiness, sincerity, and indirect commercial purpose of the influencer. Consumers trust the influencers in social media almost as much as they trust their friends. The study of Djafarova & Rushworth [9] investigated influencers and traditional celebrities' effect on purchase decisions of young women who are Instagram users. The study findings show that influencers were more effective on the purchase decisions of young female Instagram users than traditional celebrities [9].

2. Brand image

Brand image is a consumer's perception about a brand as a reflection of the brand association that exists in their mind. Brand image is a band of brand association that occurs in the consumer's mind. Brand image is a type of association that occurs in their minds when they remember about a particular brand. Brand image is what consumers think and feel when they hear or see a brand and what the consumer is studying about a brand. [10] . Brand image is a strong perception in the consumer's mind about a brand that is framed from consumer's memory toward that brand. An established brand will have a strong position in the competition

if supported by a lot of strong associations. A lot of strong brand associations are related that will create a brand image. The more association is related, the stronger the brand image created by the brand. Brand image is a band of brand association that is created in the consumer's mind [10]

3. Brand awareness

Brand awareness is the willingness of a customer to recognize, remember a brand as one of the particular products [10]. Brand awareness is the consumer's ability to identify the brand in a different condition, which is reflected by brand recognition or recall performance. Brand awareness is the brand's ability to occur in the consumer's mind when the consumer is thinking of some product and how easy the name occurs [11] Metrics that used to measure brand awareness, are the easiness of consumers to recognize a brand, the easiness for the consumer to remember a brand, the awareness of consumers toward product existence, how often the consumer watches the advertisement in media [11]

4. Brand trust

Brand trust is a process that is "thought out and carefully designed," and brand loyalty is formed. Brand trust is defined as "the willingness of the average consumer to rely on the ability of the brand to perform its stated function" [12]. Brand trust is a fundamental concept for brand relationships because, in addition to increasing brand loyalty, it strengthens and manages the relationship between customer and business [13]. Brand trust consists of two dimensions: trustworthiness and intentions. Trustworthiness is about meeting promises and satisfying needs. The intentions are about the goodwill and attitudinal behavior shown to the client when faced with a problem. The more available these features are the more trust for the brand [14]

5. Purchasing decision

The purchase decision is a process when a consumer is trying to identify a problem, looking for information about a product or particular brand, and evaluate how good each alternative can solve their problem, which is then leading to purchase decisions. The purchase decision is a process that consists of several stages which consumers do before purchasing a product [15] Purchase intention and the desire to purchase are two components of the purchase decision process. Ads which are shared on social media can catch consumer attention and encourage them to check the product or service, which could create a purchase intention. Consequently, social media can affect the pre-purchase stage and purchase intention of consumers [16]

6. Relationship Brand Trust, Influencer and Languages

High arousal language refers to language that is emotionally charged, such as "amazing" or "incredible." The authors found that high arousal language increases engagement with micro influencers, but it decreases engagement with macro influencers. This is because high arousal language makes micro influencers appear more trustworthy, while it makes macro influencers appear less trustworthy.[17] From those research can be found that followers express more trust when micro influencers use high arousal language, and the negative effect of high arousal language for macro influencers is mitigated when the post has a more informative than commercial goal or if they include trustworthiness cues in their posts. Overall, the study from Rizzo at 2022 [17] highlights the importance of language in shaping consumer behavior and the need for marketers to carefully consider the language used by influencers in their sponsored posts and suggests that businesses should focus on building trust with their audience by using informative language and including trustworthiness cues in their posts.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

This conceptual framework outlines the effect of micro and macro Brand ambassadors in related to soft and hard selling language with purchasing decisions on Piero. It consists of four key stages : deciding the digital Brand ambassadors to review the Piero shoes, deciding the soft selling and hard selling language that will be used by the brand ambassadors on their instagram account, compare the effect of the brand ambassadors related to the language with brand trust, brand awareness, brand image and compare the effect of the micro and macro brand ambassadors related to the soft and hard selling language with purchasing decision. The comparison will be used to give the business recommendation to Piero's company which type of the brand ambassador's that they should collaborate with

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

RESEARCH DESIGN

Research designs are plans and procedures for research that span the decisions from broad assumptions to detailed methods of data collection and analysis [18]. Research seeks to develop relevant, true statements, ones that can serve to explain the situation of concern or that describe the causal relationships of interest. In quantitative studies, researchers advance the relationship among variables and pose this in terms of questions or hypotheses.

This research uses quantitative methodology, focusing on the effect of the brand ambassadors related to soft and hard selling language with brand trust, brand awareness, brand image and the purchasing decision of the Piero shoes. The Multi anova analysis is used to compare the effect between those variable’s then the research continues to the competitor analysis. The result of the research is the business recommendation for Piero shoes.

Figure 2. Research Design

DATA COLLECTION METHOD

The research made an experiment designed to investigate the impact of high arousal language on consumer engagement with micro versus macro influencers. The study also explores the role of persuasion knowledge in this process. To conduct the study, the authors recruited 339 participants from an online social media site. The participants were randomly assigned to one of four conditions: micro influencer with high arousal language, micro influencer with low arousal language, macro influencer with high arousal language, and macro influencer with low arousal language. They were then asked to view an Instagram post by the assigned influencer and rate their engagement with the post. For the data collection the author used primary and secondary data, for primary data we used interviews and questionnaires and for secondary data we used books, articles and online journals

VARIABLES

To answer the research question, this research needs to collect data on the following variables:

1. Macro brand Ambassador and micro brand ambassador

This variable chosen by the author in order be divided into different groups and then will be compared. As in Micro KOL (Key Opinion Leader) is Adityalogy with 80.900 followers instagram which is a musician also figure trusted for shoes review. Meanwhile Macro KOL (Key Opinion Leader) is Ari Lesmana with 686.000 followers instagram which is musician as vocalist fourtenty band and figure who tend to receive instagram endorsement.

2. Soft and hard selling language

Each group is divided again into 2 groups, based on different styles of language. Therefore the total group is 4, and there are : Micro KOL (Key Opinion Leader) with soft language, Micro KOL (Key Opinion Leader) with hard language, Macro KOL (Key Opinion Leader) with soft language and Macro KOL (Key Opinion Leader) with hard language.

Soft language criteria is write a positive shoes review but there are no superfluous words and include sentence questions with followers. Hard language criteria is write a positive review with superfluous words such as “amazing or very good” and also state the shoe price.

3. The characteristics of the customers: age, gender, income, education and shoe preferences. These are the control variables.

These variables are gotten by asking the customers to provide demographic information and their opinions on different aspects of shoes, such as style, comfort, quality, and price.

4. Brand image

Dependent variables will be divided into 4 groups. These variables acquired by ask some questions such as :
 Does a local shoe brand need a Brand Ambassador?
 Can you know the brand logo if it's not listed?
 Have you ever seen social media influencers wear shoes on?

5. Brand awareness

Dependent variables will be divided into 4 groups. These variables acquired by ask some questions such as :
 Do you know a local shoe brand that KOL uses?
 How often have you ever heard people talk about the shoe brand above?
 When was the last time you saw people use Piero Shoes?

6. Brand trust

Dependent variables will be divided into 4 groups. These variables acquired by ask some questions such as :
 How much do you trust with shoes reviewed by KOL?
 How much do you really trust that Piero shoes are really suitable with reviews by KOL on social media? For those who have already purchased, is Piero shoes quality suitable with the price?

7. Purchasing decision

Dependent variables will be divided into 4 groups. These variables acquired by ask some questions such as :
 What possibilities would you recommend Piero shoes to friends & family?
 What is the main reason you decide to buy Piero Shoes?
 Do you really trust the KOL (Key Opinion Leader) review and decide to buy Piero shoes?
 This research collects these variable's data using surveys and questionnaires (See the appendix)

DATA ANALYSIS METHOD

The final data project used primary data to do the analysis. The primary data is given from the answer of the questionnaire. The primary data is used to get the comparison effect of the micro and macro brand ambassadors related to the soft and hard selling language with brand trust, brand awareness, brand image and the purchasing decision. This research uses MULTI ANOVA analysis for comparing the mean participants answer's of brand trust, brand awareness, brand image and purchasing decision of the four groups after the intervention to them.

RESULT

Table 1. questionnaire result

Questions	Micro KOL ADITYALOGY Soft Selling (%) n=76	Micro KOL ADITYALOGY Hard Selling (%) n=87	Macro KOL ARI LESMANA Soft Selling (%) n=88	Macro KOL ARI LESMANA Hard Selling (%) n=88
Gender	Male 71.1% Female 28.9%	Male 66.7% Female 33.3%	Male 89.8% Female 10.2%	Male 87.5% Female 12.5%
Age	15-20 thn : 9.2% 21-26 thn : 43.4%	15-20 thn : 8% 21-26 thn : 52.9%	15-20 thn : 3.4% 21-26 thn : 48.9%	15-20 thn :9.1% 21-26 thn :30.7%

	27-32 thn : 30.3% 33-40 thn : 15.8% >40 thn : 1.2%	27-32 thn : 25.3% 33-40 thn : 8% >40 thn :5.8%	27-32 thn : 28.4% 33-40 thn : 14.8% >40 thn : 4.5%	27-32 thn : 23.9% 33-40 thn :23.9% >40 thn :12.5%
Occupation				
-Student	14.5%	21.8%	26.1%	21.6%
-Employee	55.3%	55.2%	42%	50%
-Freelance	11.8%	9.2%	9.1%	14.8%
-Entrepreneur	14.5%	9.2%	6.8%	6.8%
Income per month	< 5 juta 23.7% 5-10 juta 50% >10 juta 26.3%	< 5 juta 23.3% 5-10 juta 53.5% >10 juta 23.3%	< 5 juta 62.5% 5-10 juta 27.3% >10 juta 10.2%	< 5 juta 50% 5-10 juta 33% >10 juta 17%
Platform use when buy local shoe				
Website				
Tokopedia	22.4%	35.6%	13.6%	8.1%
Shopee	38.2%	37.9%	43.2%	54.7%
InstagramShop	26.3%	14.9%	40.9%	37.2%
TiktokShop	11.8%	10.3%	1.1%	0%
	1.3%	1.1%	1.1%	0%
Have you ever bought local shoes?				
Yes				
Never	77.3%	85.1%	96.6%	89.8%
	22.7%	14.9%	3.4%	10.2%
Where do you know about local shoe brands?				
Friends family	33.3%	33.3%	17%	25%
Digital ads	29.3%	29.9%	33%	28.4%
Influencer	21.3%	24.1%	44.3%	36.4%
Offline ads	16%	12.6%	5.7%	10.2%
Which one do you like for these shoe designs?				

design 1	25.3%	34.6%	16.1%	26.1%
design 2	41.3%	36%	52.9%	38.6%
design 3	33.3%	29.1%	31%	35.2%
What is your main consideration when buying a local shoe brand?				
-good quality	76%	78.2%	58%	63.6%
-used by influencer	14.7%	12.6%	15.9%	17%
-discount promo	9.3%	9.2%	25.1%	19.3%
Do you think local shoe brands need a Brand Ambassador?				
yes	93.2%	93.1%	87.4%	94.3%
no	6.8%	6.9%	12.6%	5.7%
Do you know this influencer above?				
Yes	67.6%	70.6%	68.2%	57.5%
No	32.4%	29.4%	31.8%	42.5%
Do you follow this influencer instagram above?				
Yes	30.3%	28.7%	10.2%	2.3%
no	69.7%	71.3%	89.8%	97.7%
Do you know the shoes that this influencer wears?				
Yes	39.5%	36.8%	60.2%	59.1%
No	60.2%	63.2%	39.8%	40.9%
Do you think this				

influencer is suitable to represent a local brand?				
yes	73.7%	73.6%	45.5%	45.5%
no	6.6%	2.3%	17%	13.6%
undecided	19.7%	24.1%	37.5%	40.9%
How often do you hear people talk about the local shoe brand above? (1 Never, 5 very often)	1 = 25% 2 = 13.2% 3 = 26.3% 4 = 18.4% 5 = 17.1%	1 = 18.6% 2 = 11.6% 3 = 29.1% 4 = 26.7% 5 = 14%	1 = 14.9% 2 = 16.1% 3 = 34.5% 4 = 27.6% 5 = 6.9%	1 = 13.6% 2 = 21.6% 3 = 44.3% 4 = 17% 5 = 3.4%
When was the last time you saw people wear the local shoe brand above? (1 never 5 very often)	1 = 21.1% 2 = 11.8% 3 = 23.7% 4 = 15.8% 5 = 27.6%	1 = 11.8% 2 = 11.8% 3 = 29.4% 4 = 16.5% 5 = 30.6%	1 = 18.6% 2 = 16.3% 3 = 29.1% 4 = 17.4% 5 = 18.6%	1 = 23% 2 = 25.3% 3 = 21.8% 4 = 8% 5 = 21.8%
Have you ever bought this local shoe brand above? (1 never, 5 very often)	1 = 57.9% 2 = 13.2% 3 = 15.8% 4 = 10.5% 5 = 2.6%	1 = 50.6% 2 = 9.2% 3 = 24.1% 4 = 4.6% 5 = 11.5%	1 = 62.5% 2 = 6.8% 3 = 13.6% 4 = 12.5% 5 = 4.5%	1 = 65.9% 2 = 5.7% 3 = 14.8% 4 = 9.1% 5 = 4.5%
Do you think this local shoe brand above is suitable with the price? (1 unsuitable, 5 very suitable)	1 = 15.9% 2 = 4.8% 3 = 36.5% 4 = 27% 5 = 15.9%	1 = 4% 2 = 12% 3 = 40% 4 = 22.7% 5 = 21.3%	1 = 6.75% 2 = 6.7% 3 = 22.2% 4 = 28.9% 5 = 35.6%	1 = 4.5% 2 = 0% 3 = 36.4% 4 = 38.6% 5 = 20.5%
Can you know the brand's logo properly?	1 = 21.3% 2 = 17.3% 3 = 17.3% 4 = 20%	1 = 22.1% 2 = 12.8% 3 = 30.2% 4 = 18.6%	1 = 31.8% 2 = 10.2% 3 = 8% 4 = 19.3%	1 = 25.3% 2 = 12.6% 3 = 18.4% 4 = 23%

(1 didn't know, 5 very know)	5 = 24%	5 = 16.3%	5 = 30.7%	5=20.7%
Have you ever seen influencers in social media wear the local shoe brand above? (1 never, 5 very often)	1 = 17.3% 2 = 5.3% 3 = 36% 4 = 25.3% 5 = 16%	1 = 20.9% 2 = 17.4% 3 = 30.2% 4 = 17.4% 5 = 14%	1 = 30.7% 2 = 10.2% 3 = 27.3% 4 = 20.5% 5 = 11.4%	1=33% 2=14.8% 3=26.1% 4=20.5% 5=5.7%
Will you recommend this local shoe brand above to your friends & family? (1 never, 5 will highly recommend)	1 = 4% 2 = 4% 3 = 32% 4 = 33.3% 5 = 26.7%	1 =2.4% 2 =7.1% 3 =38.8% 4 =23.5% 5 =28.2%	1 = 4.5% 2 = 10.2% 3 = 35.2% 4 = 37.5% 5 = 12.5%	1 =2.3% 2 =6.8% 3 =37.5% 4 =37.5% 5 =15.9%
How much do you trust the shoes reviewed by this influencer? (1 didn't trust, 5 very trust)	1 = 2.7% 2 = 6.7% 3 = 34.7% 4 = 37.3% 5 = 18.7%	1 = 1.2% 2 = 5.8% 3 = 36% 4 = 29.1% 5 = 27.9%	1 = 4.6% 2 = 12.6% 3 = 48.3% 4 = 27.6% 5 = 6.9%	1=3.4% 2=6.8% 3=43.2% 4=37.5% 5=9.1%
Do you really trust that the Piero brand is really suitable with what influencer said in social media? (1 didn't trust, 5 very trust)	1 = 2.7% 2 = 2.7% 3 = 36% 4 = 37.3% 5 = 21.3%	1 = 1.2% 2 = 4.7% 3 = 31.4% 4 = 34.9% 5 = 27.9%	1 = 9.2% 2 = 9.2% 3 = 46% 4 = 27.6% 5 = 8%	1=3.4% 2=5.7% 3=43.2% 4=38.6% 5=9.1%
If you finally decide to buy Piero, what is				

your main consideration when buying Piero? 1.Never buy 2.Because trust with influencer 3.Trust that Piero have a good quality 4. Because ever bought Piero before 5. Because Piero has been established since 20 years ago	1 = 6.6% 2 = 10.5% 3 = 47.4% 4 = 21.1% 5 = 14.5%	1 = 3.5% 2 = 11.6% 3 = 48.8% 4 = 12.8% 5 = 23.3%	1 =12.6% 2 = 6.9% 3 =47.1% 4 =26.4% 5 =6.9%	1=6.8% 2=17% 3=48.9% 4=21.6% 5=5.7%
After seeing the review by an influencer, do you trust and decide to buy Piero? 1.Didn't trust and will not buy 2. Quietly trust, should see directly 3. Undecided 4. Trust but not directly buy 5. Trust and directly buy	1 = 5.3% 2 = 13.2% 3 = 18.4% 4 = 51.3% 5 = 11.8%	1 = 2.4% 2 = 3.5% 3 = 34.1% 4 = 42.4% 5 = 17.6%	1 =1.1% 2 =21.6% 3 =13.6% 4 =61.4% 5 =2.3%	1=3.4% 2=13.6% 3=14.8% 4=63.6% 5=4.5%

After completing a questionnaire, the author conducted reliability test use Cronbach with result should above 0.6 and validity test use Pearson should below 0.6. And the result from the reliability test can be seen at Table 2.

Table 2. Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.890	11

And the result from the validity questionnaire is 0.000 use Pearson.

From the two results above, the questionnaire in this research is valid and reliable.

From a total 339 questionnaire respondents, which is dominated by men is Micro Brand Ambassador soft selling with total amount 71.1%, Also with Micro Brand Ambassador hard selling dominated by men with total amount 66.7%. For Macro Brand Ambassador soft selling and hard selling, also dominated with men with a total amount 89.8% and 87.5%.

As can be seen at table 1 from each group, respondents dominated the age range 21 - 26 years old. The total amount from Micro Brand Ambassador soft selling is 43.4%, followed by Micro Brand Ambassador hard selling with total amount 52.9%, and then Macro Brand Ambassador soft selling with total amount 48.9%, followed by Macro Brand Ambassador hard selling with total amount 30.7%.

Questionnaire respondents dominated with employees as can be seen at Table 1 Micro Brand Ambassador soft selling with total amount 55.3% followed by Micro Brand Ambassador hard selling with total amount 55.2%. For Macro Brand Ambassador soft selling the total amount is 42% and for hard selling is 50%. This could happen because employees have their own income so they can buy things independently.

Almost all questionnaire respondents have ever bought local shoe brands as can be seen at Table 1. For Micro Brand Ambassador soft selling the total amount is 77.3%, followed by Micro Brand Ambassador hard selling with total amount 85.1%. And then for Macro Brand Ambassador soft selling total amount is 96.6%, followed by Macro Brand Ambassador with total amount 89.8%. It means that all questionnaire respondents have been familiar with shoe brands made in Indonesia.

Based on the results from Table 1, almost all questionnaire respondents think that local shoe brands need Brand Ambassador. This thing can be seen from the data that Micro Brand Ambassador soft language with total amount 93.2%, followed by Micro Brand Ambassador hard selling with total 93.1%. And then for Macro Brand Ambassador soft selling with a total amount 87.4% followed by Macro Brand Ambassador hard selling with total 94.3%.

BRAND AWARENESS ANALYSIS

In table 1 in the question section "Do you know the shoes worn by the influencer?", there are quite significant differences between the micro brand Ambassador group and the macro brand Ambassador group. For more details, see table 3 below

Table 3. brand awareness

Questions	Micro KOL ADITYALOGY Soft Selling (%) n=76	Micro KOL ADITYALOGY Hard Selling (%) n=87	Macro KOL ARI LESMANA Soft Selling (%) n=88	Macro KOL ARI LESMANA Hard Selling (%) n=88
Do you know the shoes that this influencer wears?				
Yes	39.5%	36.8%	60.2%	59.1%
No	60.2%	63.2%	39.8%	40.9%

As can be seen in more detail at Table 3 respondents from Micro Brand Ambassador soft selling group with total amount 39.5% and Micro Brand Ambassador hard selling with total amount 36.8% know the shoes brand that Micro KOL (Adityalogy) wear. Meanwhile for Macro Brand Ambassador (Ari Lesmana), more respondents know the shoes brand that KOL wear, for Macro Brand Ambassador soft selling total is 60.2% and for Macro Brand Ambassador hard selling with total amount 59.1%.

As can be seen at Adityalogy's Instagram, the brand ambassador or influencer has never worn the shoes used (Piero) in this research. Adityalogy brand ambassadors often wear Compass and Parabellum shoes. Meanwhile, the macro brand ambassador, Ari Lesmana, was a PIERO model around the beginning of 2023, so it is natural that participants still recognize the brand of shoes that Ari Lesmana wears.

The question above reflects brand awareness, however to assess the effectiveness of Micro and Macro Brand Ambassadors on brand awareness, we have to look at other questions as seen at table 4 and then analyze them statistically using SPSS 22.

Table 4. Brand awareness

Questions	Micro KOL ADITYALOGY Soft Selling (%) n=76	Micro KOL ADITYALOGY Hard Selling (%) n=87	Macro KOL ARI LESMANA Soft Selling (%) n=88	Macro KOL ARI LESMANA Hard Selling (%) n=88
Can you know the brand's logo properly? (1 didn't know, 5 very know)	1 = 21.3% 2 = 17.3% 3 = 17.3% 4 = 20% 5 = 24%	1 = 22.1% 2 = 12.8% 3 = 30.2% 4 = 18.6% 5 = 16.3%	1 = 31.8% 2 = 10.2% 3 = 8% 4 = 19.3% 5 = 30.7%	1 = 25.3% 2 = 12.6% 3 = 18.4% 4 = 23% 5 = 20.7%
Have you ever seen influencers in social media wear the local shoe brand above? (1 never, 5 very often)	1 = 17.3% 2 = 5.3% 3 = 36% 4 = 25.3% 5 = 16%	1 = 20.9% 2 = 17.4% 3 = 30.2% 4 = 17.4% 5 = 14%	1 = 30.7% 2 = 10.2% 3 = 27.3% 4 = 20.5% 5 = 11.4%	1 = 33% 2 = 14.8% 3 = 26.1% 4 = 20.5% 5 = 5.7%
How often do you hear people talk about the local shoe brand above? (1 Never, 5 very often)	1 = 25% 2 = 13.2% 3 = 26.3% 4 = 18.4% 5 = 17.1%	1 = 18.6% 2 = 11.6% 3 = 29.1% 4 = 26.7% 5 = 14%	1 = 14.9% 2 = 16.1% 3 = 34.5% 4 = 27.6% 5 = 6.9%	1 = 13.6% 2 = 21.6% 3 = 44.3% 4 = 17% 5 = 3.4%
When was the last time you saw people wear the local shoe brand above?	1 = 21.1% 2 = 11.8% 3 = 23.7% 4 = 15.8% 5 = 27.6%	1 = 11.8% 2 = 11.8% 3 = 29.4% 4 = 16.5% 5 = 30.6%	1 = 18.6% 2 = 16.3% 3 = 29.1% 4 = 17.4% 5 = 18.6%	1 = 23% 2 = 25.3% 3 = 21.8% 4 = 8% 5 = 21.8%
(1 never 5 very often)				

From table 4 it is then processed using SPSS 22 with MULTI ANOVA, with the following results

Table 5. ANOVA TEST MICRO VS MACRO

micromacro	Seberapa sering kamu mendengar orang-orang membicarakan tentang brand sepatu lokal diatas?	1.484	1	1.484	.981	.323
→	Kapan terakhir kali kamu melihat ada orang yang memakai brand sepatu lokal diatas?	15.318	1	15.318	7.520	.006
	Apakah kamu dapat mengenali logo brand sepatu lokal diatas dengan baik? (Jika tidak dicantumkan nama brandnya)	.235	1	.235	.103	.749
→	Apakah kamu pernah melihat ada influencer di social media memakai sepatu brand lokal diatas?	11.855	1	11.855	6.807	.009

in table 5 the results of the answers to questions that reflect the effectiveness of micro and macro KOL related to soft and hard selling language on the brand awareness variable in table 4 are compared between the micro and macro brand Ambassador groups, the results are : the two questions that produce significant differences between the macro and macro groups micro brand ambassadors and there are :

“When was the last time you saw someone wearing a local shoe brand above?” with $p = 0.006$

"Have you ever seen any influencer on social media wearing the local brand shoes above?" with $p = 0.009$

Table 6. Anova Test Soft Selling Language Vs Hard Selling Language

softhard	Seberapa sering kamu mendengar orang-orang membicarakan tentang brand sepatu lokal diatas?	.077	1	.077	.051	.822
	Kapan terakhir kali kamu melihat ada orang yang memakai brand sepatu lokal diatas?	.159	1	.159	.078	.780
	Apakah kamu dapat mengenali logo brand sepatu lokal diatas dengan baik? (Jika tidak dicantumkan nama brandnya)	.802	1	.802	.351	.554
	Apakah kamu pernah melihat ada influencer di social media memakai sepatu brand lokal diatas?	5.132	1	5.132	2.947	.087

Meanwhile, in table 6 it can be seen that the results of the answers to questions that reflect the effectiveness of micro and macro KOL related to soft and hard selling language on the brand awareness variable between soft and hard selling as a whole do not have a statistically significant difference.

Table 7. ANOVA TEST Micro and soft selling, Micro and hard selling, macro and soft selling, macro and hard selling

micromacro * softhard						
Seberapa sering kamu mendengar orang-orang membicarakan tentang brand sepatu lokal diatas?	1.494	1	1.494	.988	.321	
Kapan terakhir kali kamu melihat ada orang yang memakai brand sepatu lokal diatas?	2.481	1	2.481	1.218	.271	
Apakah kamu dapat mengenali logo brand sepatu lokal diatas dengan baik? (Jika tidak dicantumkan nama brandnya)	.351	1	.351	.154	.695	
Apakah kamu pernah melihat ada influencer di social media memakai sepatu brand lokal diatas?	.522	1	.522	.300	.584	

Meanwhile, in table 7 it can be seen that the results of the answers to questions that reflect the effectiveness of micro and macro KOL related to soft and hard selling language on the brand awareness variable are compared between the four groups, it turns out the results are not significantly different.

To see further explanation, you can see Figure 3, which reflects a comparison graph of the answers between the micro and macro brand ambassador groups to the question "When was the last time you saw someone wearing the local shoe brand above?" with p = 0.006

Estimated Marginal Means of Kapan terakhir kali kamu melihat ada orang yang memakai brand sepatu lokal diatas?

Figure 3. Compare chart micro and macro ambassador related to soft and selling language

From the picture, it can be seen that the micro group with hard selling language is the group with the most effective average (mean) answers compared to the other three groups. Even the results from the micro group with soft selling language delivered were still more effective when compared to the results in the macro group with soft or hard selling language delivered.

In Figure 4, you can see a comparison graph of the results of answers related to brand awareness regarding "Have you ever seen any influencer on social media wearing the local brand shoes above?" with $p = 0.009$

Figure 4. Compare chart micro and macro ambassador related to soft and selling language

From Figure 4, it can be seen that the average (mean) results in the micro brand ambassador group using soft selling language achieved the most effective results when compared to the results of the other three groups. The average (mean) answer results for the Micro brand ambassador group using hard selling language were also still higher compared to the answer results for the macro brand ambassador group, whether using soft selling or hard selling language.

Looking at the results in table 5 table 6 table 7 and figure 3 and figure 4 it can be concluded that micro brand ambassadors are still significantly more effective for brand awareness when compared to macro brand ambassadors, whatever the language in this research.

BRAND IMAGE ANALYSIS

Table 8. Brand image and relation to purchasing decision

Questions	Micro KOL ADITYALOGY Soft Selling (%) n=76	Micro KOL ADITYALOGY Hard Selling (%) n=87	Macro KOL ARI LESMANA Soft Selling (%) n=88	Macro KOL ARI LESMANA Hard Selling (%) n=88
What is your main consideration when buying a local shoe brand?				
-good quality	76%	78.2%	58%	63.6%
-used by influencer	14.7%	12.6%	15.9%	17%
-discount promo	9.3%	9.2%	25.1%	19.3%

From the questions at table 8 submitted show the results that of the four groups the majority of questionnaire participants consider that they buy shoes because the image of the quality of local shoes must be good first with results of 76% in the Micro brand ambassador group with soft selling language, 78.2% in the micro group brand ambassador with hard selling language, 58% in the macro brand ambassador and soft selling language group, and 63.6% in the macro Kol group with hard selling language. Based on the data above alone, this means that the majority of participants buy because a local brand must have good quality.

Table 9. Brand image and related to purchasing decision

Questions	Micro KOL ADITYALOGY Soft Selling (%) n=76	Micro KOL ADITYALOGY Hard Selling (%) n=87	Macro KOL ARI LESMANA Soft Selling (%) n=88	Macro KOL ARI LESMANA Hard Selling (%) n=88
Do you think this local shoe brand above is suitable with the price? (1 unsuitable, 5 very suitable)	1 = 15.9% 2 = 4.8% 3 = 36.5% 4 = 27 % 5 = 15.9%	1 = 4% 2 = 12% 3 = 40% 4 = 22.7% 5 = 21.3%	1 = 6.75 2 = 6.7% 3 = 22.2% 4 = 28.9% 5 = 35.6%	1 = 4.5% 2 = 0 % 3 = 36.4% 4 = 38.6% 5 = 20.5%
If you finally decide to buy				
Piero, what is your main consideration when buying Piero? 1.Never buy 2.Because trust with influencer 3.Trust that Piero have a good quality 4. Because ever bought Piero before 5. Because Piero has been established since 20 years ago	1 = 6.6% 2 = 10.5% 3 = 47.4% 4 = 21.1% 5 = 14.5%	1 = 3.5% 2 = 11.6% 3 = 48.8% 4 = 12.8% 5 = 23.3%	1 =12.6% 2 = 6.9% 3 =47.1% 4 =26.4% 5 =6.9%	1=6.8% 2=17% 3=48.9% 4=21.6% 5=5.7%

To be more effective in assessing brand image and purchasing decisions, you can look at the questions in table 9, which will then be analyzed using MULTI ANOVA in SPSS 22.

Table 10. Brand image and related to purchasing decision

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
micromacro	Bagi yang sudah pernah membeli, apakah kualitas brand sepatu lokal diatas sudah sesuai dengan harganya?	16.690	1	16.690	7.358	.007
	<p>Dari skala 1-5, jika anda akhirnya memutuskan untuk membeli Sepatu Piero setelah mengisi survey ini, apa alasan anda akhirnya memutuskan untuk membeli Sepatu Piero?</p> <p>1 = Saya tidak akan membeli 2 = Saya percaya dengan review yang diucapkan oleh Brand Ambassador/influencer/KOL 3 = Saya percaya bahwa Sepatu Piero memiliki kualitas yang bagus 4 = Saya sudah pernah membeli Sepatu Piero sebelumnya jadi saya percaya bahwa Sepatu Piero memiliki kualitas yang bagus 5 = Saya percaya karena Sepatu Piero sudah berusia lebih dari 20 tahun</p>	1.906	1	1.906	1.646	.201

In table 10, it can be seen that there is a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.007$) in the average answers between the two groups, namely micro brand ambassadors and macro brand ambassadors, to the question "for those who have already purchased, is the quality of the local shoes above appropriate for the price? ?" This question reflects the brand image, whether PIERO shoes which are the object of research already have a brand image of good quality or not.

Table 11. Brand image and related to purchasing decision

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
softhard	Bagi yang sudah pernah membeli, apakah kualitas brand sepatu lokal diatas sudah sesuai dengan harganya?	62.719	1	62.719	27.651	.000
	Dari skala 1-5, jika anda akhirnya memutuskan untuk membeli Sepatu Piero setelah mengisi survey ini, apa alasan anda akhirnya memutuskan untuk membeli Sepatu Piero? 1 = Saya tidak akan membeli 2 = Saya percaya dengan review yang diucapkan oleh Brand Ambassador/Influencer/KOL 3 = Saya percaya bahwa Sepatu Piero memiliki kualitas yang bagus 4 = Saya sudah pernah membeli Sepatu Piero sebelumnya jadi saya percaya bahwa Sepatu Piero memiliki kualitas yang bagus 5 = Saya percaya karena Sepatu Piero sudah berusia lebih dari 20 tahun	1.774	1	1.774	1.532	.217

Meanwhile, in table 11 it can be seen that there is a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.000$) in the average answers between the two groups, namely soft selling language and hard selling language to the question "for those who have already bought, is the quality of the local shoes above appropriate for the price? ?

Table 12. Brand image and related to purchasing decision

Tests of Between-Subjects Effects

Source	Dependent Variable	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
micromacro * softhard	Bagi yang sudah pernah membeli, apakah kualitas brand sepatu lokal diatas sudah sesuai dengan harganya?	36.995	1	36.995	16.310	.000
	Dari skala 1-5, jika anda akhirnya memutuskan untuk membeli Sepatu Piero setelah mengisi survey ini, apa alasan anda akhirnya memutuskan untuk membeli Sepatu Piero?					
	1 = Saya tidak akan membeli 2 = Saya percaya dengan review yang diucapkan oleh Brand Ambassador/influencer/KOL 3 = Saya percaya bahwa Sepatu Piero memiliki kualitas yang bagus 4 = Saya sudah pernah membeli Sepatu Piero sebelumnya jadi saya percaya bahwa Sepatu Piero memiliki kualitas yang bagus 5 = Saya percaya karena Sepatu Piero sudah berusia lebih dari 20 tahun	.430	1	.430	.371	.543

Then in table 12, when what is compared is the average answer to the question "for those who have already purchased, is the quality of the local shoes above appropriate for the price?" In the 4 groups, namely: micro brand ambassadors with soft selling language, micro brand ambassadors with hard selling language, macro brand ambassadors with soft selling language, and macro brand ambassadors with hard selling language, there was a statistically significant difference, namely $p=0.000$

In Figure 5 we get the average results for answers to the question "For those who have already bought them, is the quality of the local shoes above appropriate for the price?" which reflects the brand image that the Macro brand ambassador group with hard selling language has a higher average answer than the answers of the other three groups. The answers with the lowest mean answers were found in the macro brand ambassador group with hard selling delivery. This difference based on table 10, table 11 and 12 is statistically significant.

Figure 5 Compare chart micro and macro ambassador related to soft and selling language with multi-anova on spss 22

Meanwhile, from Figure 6 which reflects the question of why they bought Piero shoes, and its relationship with brand image, the results showed that between the four groups the average answer was between a scale of 3-3.4, which means scale 3 on the question of what reasons ultimately made participants buy PIERO shoes. produces the answer "I bought because PIERO has good quality". Because the majority of answers to the 4 groups ranged from scale 3, in the end it did not produce a statistically significant difference, or could be interpreted as having similar answers.

As for Figure 6 it is shown that the micro brand ambassador group with hard language delivery is higher than the other three groups, however this difference is not statistically significant after checking through MULTI ANOVA, as attached in table 10, table 11 and table 12.

Figure 6. Compare chart micro and macro ambassador related to soft and selling language with brand image and purchasing decision using multi-anova on spss 22

Based on the results of table 10, table 11, and table 12 and figure 5 which are the results of analysis using MULTI ANOVA in SPSS 22, it can be concluded in this research that brand image is more effectively displayed through macro brand ambassador groups with hard selling delivery when compared to groups others. This is in accordance with the literature which states that one of the benefits of Macro influencers is that they can increase the image representation of a product.

Meanwhile, based on Figure 6, it can be concluded from this study that in all groups, the main reason participants will buy PIERO shoes is because they believe in the good quality of Piero (scale 3). The answers between all of four groups also did not differ significantly. ($p > 0.05$)

This result can happen because PIERO is already 22 years old in Indonesia, and has succeeded in building an image as a quality local shoe brand.

BRAND TRUST ANALYSIS

The most effective question from the questionnaire to measure the Brand trust is

“How much do you trust the local shoe reviews above by the following influencers?” and also Do you really believe the Piero Brand is what the influencer says on social media?

The result of the both questions are shown at the table 13

Table 13. Brand trust

Questions	Micro KOL ADITYALOGY Soft Selling (%) n=76	Micro KOL ADITYALOGY Hard Selling (%) n=87	Macro KOL ARI LESMANA Soft Selling (%) n=88	Macro KOL ARI LESMANA Hard Selling (%) n=88
How much do you trust the shoes reviewed by this influencer? (1 didn't trust, 5 very trust)	1 = 2.7% 2 = 6.7% 3 = 34.7% 4 = 37.3% 5 = 18.7%	1 = 1.2% 2 = 5.8% 3 = 36% 4 = 29.1% 5 = 27.9%	1 = 4.6% 2 = 12.6% 3 = 48.3% 4 = 27.6% 5 = 6.9%	1=3.4% 2=6.8% 3=43.2% 4=37.5% 5=9.1%
Do you really trust that the Piero brand is really suitable with what influencer said in social media? (1 didn't trust, 5 very trust)	1 = 2.7% 2 = 2.7% 3 = 36% 4 = 37.3% 5 = 21.3%	1 = 1.2% 2 = 4.7% 3 = 31.4% 4 = 34.9% 5 = 27.9%	1 = 9.2% 2 = 9.2% 3 = 46% 4 = 27.6% 5 = 8%	1=3.4% 2=5.7% 3=43.2% 4=38.6% 5=9.1%

To assess the comparison of the results of the answers to questions in table 4.12, analysis then using MULTI ANOVA in SPSS 22 with the following results

Table 14. Brand trust analysis with multi in SPSS 22

micromacro	Dari skala 1-5, seberapa percayakah anda mengenai review sepatu piero oleh sosok Micro KOL diatas (Adityalogy)?	14.151	1	14.151	15.887	.000
	Dari skala 1-5, apakah anda benar-benar percaya bahwa brand piero sesuai dengan apa yang dia (Adityalogy) katakan di media sosial?	20.839	1	20.839	22.935	.000
softhard	Dari skala 1-5, seberapa percayakah anda mengenai review sepatu piero oleh sosok Micro KOL diatas (Adityalogy)?	3.238	1	3.238	3.635	.057
	Dari skala 1-5, apakah anda benar-benar percaya bahwa brand piero sesuai dengan apa yang dia (Adityalogy) katakan di media sosial?	3.785	1	3.785	4.166	.042

In table 14 the answers to questions reflecting brand trust were analyzed using multi anova in SPSS 22. When the results of the answers from the two questions were compared between the MICRO ambassador and MACRO ambassador groups, it turned out to produce a statistically significant difference ($p = 0.000$). Meanwhile, when the two questions were compared between the SOFT selling language and HARD selling language groups, it resulted in a significant difference, namely in the answer to the question "How much do you trust the local shoe review above by the following influencer?" resulted in $p=0.057$ and the answer to the question "Do you really believe Brand Piero is what the influencer says on social media?" produces $p=0.042$.

Figures 7 and 8 show in more detail the comparison of the average answers to the two previous questions between the four groups as follows.

Figure 7. Compare chart micro and macro ambassador related to soft and selling language with brand trust using multi-anova on spss 22

Figure 8. Compare chart micro and macro ambassador related to soft and selling language with brand trust using multi-anova on spss 22

From figures 7 and 8, it can be seen that the Micro brand ambassador group who delivered hard selling language had a higher average answer than the other three groups. Meanwhile, the lowest average answer in both images was obtained by the Macro brand ambassador group with soft selling delivery.

Graphic figures 7 and 8 based on table 14 are statistically significantly different ($p < 0.05$). So it can be concluded from this research (using multi ANOVA analysis in SPSS 22) that the micro brand ambassador group with hard selling language delivery is more effective in terms of increasing the brand trust among customers. Meanwhile, the most ineffective in increasing brand trust is the MACRO brand ambassador group by using soft selling language.

In accordance with previous research literature states that micro influencers who make a content with high arousal language are more trusted by the public compared to macro influencers who make the content with the same language.[17] Micro influencers are believed to be more detailed when reviewing content, so the public assume they understand more than macro influencers, and of course this makes brands more effective in using marketing budgets. [17]. Meanwhile, the reason why macro influencers are less trusted is because the public thinks that it is clearly an endorsement. So they are less trusted by the public. The budget for macro influencers is also much more expensive compared to micro influencers [17]

Micro-influencers have a better understanding of their followers' preferences and needs. Micro influencers have invested time in studying their audience, learning about their interests and creating content that resonates with them. Those are the key points as valuable partners for brands [19]

PURCHASING DECISION and Brand Ambassador TRUST

The most effective question from the questionnaire to measure the purchasing decision related to the brand ambassador trust is “Setelah melihat review influencer tersebut, apakah anda percaya dan memutuskan akan membeli sepatu piero? The result can be seen at the table 15

Table 15. Brand trust and related to Purchasing decision

Questions	Micro KOL ADITYALOGY Soft Selling (%) n=76	Micro KOL ADITYALOGY Hard Selling (%) n=87	Macro KOL ARI LESMANA Soft Selling (%) n=88	Macro KOL ARI LESMANA Hard Selling (%) n=88
After seeing the review by an influencer, do you trust and decide to buy Piero?	1 = 5.3%	1 = 2.4%	1 =1.1%	1=3.4%
1.Didn't trust and will not buy	2 = 13.2%	2 = 3.5%	2 =21.6%	2=13.6%
2. Quietly trust, should see directly	3 = 18.4%	3 = 34.1%	3 =13.6%	3=14.8%
3. Undecided	4 = 51.3%	4 = 42.4%	4 =61.4%	4=63.6%
4. Trust but not directly buy	5 = 11.8%	5 = 17.6%	5 =2.3%	5=4.5%
5. Trust and directly buy				

To find out the comparison of results between the four groups, data from the answers to these questions were analyzed using multi-ANOVA in SPSS 22, with the results in table 16 as follows

Table 16. Brand trust and related to Purchasing decision analysis using multi-anova on spss 22

micromacro * softhard	Dari Skala 1-5, setelah melihat review Micro KOL (Adityalogy) tersebut, apakah anda percaya dan memutuskan akan membeli Brand Sepatu Piero?					
	1 = Tidak percaya sama sekali & tidak akan membeli	.130	1	.130	.150	.699
	2 = Kurang percaya, harus melihat secara langsung sebelum membeli					
	3 = Ragu-ragu/bingung					
	4 = Percaya tapi tidak langsung membeli					
	5 = Percaya & langsung akan membeli					
	Apakah kamu sebelumnya sudah pernah membeli sepatu brand lokal diatas?	3.746	1	3.746	2.259	.134

The mean results of the four groups' answers were not significantly different ($p > 0.699$), and if the question variable was used, "Have you previously bought the local brand shoes above?" it also turned out not to be significantly different. However, to get an idea of the answers of the four groups, you can look at the graph in Figure 9

As can be seen at the graphic results in Figure 9, the micro brand ambassador group with hard selling language has an average answer of 3.7, close to a scale of 4, (namely Trust but not immediately buy). Meanwhile, in the Macro brand ambassador group with soft selling language, the average answer on the scale was below 3.45, which means they are doubtful/confused. However, this difference is not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$) as shown in table 16

Figure 9. Compare chart micro and macro ambassador related to soft and selling language with brand trust and purchasing decision using multi-anova on spss 22

Looking at the results in table 16 and figure 9, it can be concluded that micro brand ambassadors with hard selling language are more effective in convincing customers' confidence in buying PIERO shoes compared to the other three groups, although the difference in these results is not yet significant ($p > 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

A study from *Forbes* found that 82% of consumers are more likely to purchase a product recommended by a micro influencer and of course, the money line matters. Research from *Forbes* at 2023 also found that micro influencers saw 22.2x higher conversions per week than their macro counterparts on social media platforms. [19] Influencer marketing is a form of marketing that involves people that make creative content who have a large following on social media platforms like instagram, youtube or tiktok. [20] A digital brand ambassador, as known as influencer marketing, allows brands to reach the target audience through collaboration with them. Those influencers can build a loyal and engaged audience that trust their opinions and recommendations.

Based on the explanation from the article on Dash Hudson [21] it is explained that the following are the differences in objectives in using macro and micro influencers Pros of using macro influencers :

- Increase Reach
 Macro-influencers have a higher reach than micro-influencers because they have a larger following. Because of this, their content tends to show up on explore pages, and is shared on feeds. As a result, their posts typically reach a larger audience than micro-influencer content. Working with macro-influencers is a better way to expand and increase the brand's reach in order to target new audiences.

- Key Opinion Leaders
Macro-influencers are key opinion leaders on social media that have the highest influence over consumer trends. If a macro-influencer tells their audience about a must-have product, the odds of their audience buying it are very high because of their position on social media. Working with key opinion leaders gives the brand a sense of trustworthiness.
- Drive Quick Sales
Working with macro-influencers can help drive an increase in brand sales due to their intense influence on consumer decisions. While this stands true for any type of product, it's especially effective for products that are available for a limited time only. These can trigger "Fear Of Missing Out" trends. Pros of using micro influencers :
 - Authentic Engagement
Micro-influencer tend to have authentic social engagements with their audience, meaning that their content resonates with their followers. The likes, comments, shares, and followers that micro-influencers get are all from real accounts that genuinely enjoy the content the influencer is sharing.
This authenticity drives sales because their followers trust them and are loyal to the influencer, which can often translate to the brands the influencer uses and promotes.
 - Higher ROI Potential
As mentioned, micro-influencers are much cheaper to work with than macro-influencers. Micro-influencers are focused on higher content quality, building their partnership portfolio, and connecting with their community. They tend to be interested in building their presence rather than making money from partnerships at this stage. This means working with a micro-influencer comes at a lower cost which brings in the potential for higher influencer and creator ROI.
 - Reaching Target Audience
The people that follow and support micro-influencers follow them because they are genuinely interested in the content they are posting. Micro-influencers provide very relevant content for their social media communities which in turn creates higher engagements. Finding micro-influencers that work for your brand can bring lots of awareness to your business and products. For example, if a brand focuses on health and wellness, finding a micro-influencer that promotes healthy lifestyles through exercise and healthy eating would be most effective for reaching the target audience.
 - Build Brand Ambassadors
Evidently, micro-influencers are working toward becoming macro-influencers, and brand ambassadors are working towards becoming micro-influencers to then become macro-influencers. Working with brand ambassadors can be a really great way to test out if using micro-influencers in your marketing strategy is a good fit for the brand. Starting with brand ambassadors is also probably the most cost-effective option when working with influencers. Typically with brand ambassadors you can exchange a product for a discount code for a few pieces of content per month.

CONCLUSION

Based on the result of questionnaire and the literature review, the conclusion of this research are :

1. If the author compares Micro Brand ambassador and Macro Brand ambassador at Piero, whether the language is soft or hard, Micro Brand ambassador is more effective at brand awareness, brand trust and related to the purchasing decisions than Macro Brand ambassador.
2. Micro Brand ambassador with hard selling language is the most effective ways to gain more trust and more awareness from the customer compared with other group
3. Macro Brand ambassador with hard selling language is more effective to represent the good brand image to the customer, compared with other group

RECOMMENDATION for PIERO shoes

1. To build Brand Awareness or Attention, Piero should use Micro KOL (Key Opinion Leader) with the hard selling language. The type of content such as unboxing shoes from Piero.
2. To build Interest, Piero should use Macro KOL (Key Opinion Leader) with hard selling language.

3. Piero should use both Micro and Macro KOL (Key Opinion Leader) with a soft selling or hard selling style to influence the purchase decision of customers

RECOMMENDATION for FUTURE RESEARCH

The next researcher can collect the data with women KOL (Key Opinion Leader) for Micro and Macro for the future research, because this research only uses Man Micro KOL (Key Opinion Leader) and Macro KOL (Key Opinion Leader).

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1

APPENDIX 2

Theory & reference	Purpose of questions	questions	Answers
Segmenting, Targeting, positioning	To identity respondent's demographic	Age	15-20 years Old 21-26 years Old 27-32 years Old 33-40 years Old
Segmenting, Targeting, positioning	To identity respondent's demographic	Occupation	Student College Employee Freelance / Part Timer
Segmenting, Targeting, positioning	To identity respondent's demographic	Income per month	Less than Rp 5.000.000,00 Rp 5.000.000,00 – 10.000.000,00 More than Rp 10.000.000,00
Marketing mix	To identify respondents preference	Platform used to buy local shoes?	Website Tokopedia Shopee Instagram shop Tiktok shop
Value proposition and Brand Awareness	To identify respondents preference	Which one do you like for shoe design ?	Piero jogger (picture) Piero Alaska (picture) Piero Jorge (picture)
Marketing mix	To identify respondents preference	where do you know local shoes brand	From social media ads From friends From influencer / Brand ambassador From offline promotion
Value proposition and purchasing decision	To identify respondents knowledge	Have you ever bought a pair of local shoe brands?	Yes No
Value proposition and purchasing decision	To identify respondents knowledge	Why do you buy a pair of local shoes brands?	- Has good quality - see the Brand ambassador wears the shoes - because of the promotion's that given by the brand
Brand Image	To identify respondents behavior about the brand image	From your POV, should a local brand use the Brand Ambassador to represent their image?	Scale 1-5

Influencer macro marketing	To identify respondents behavior about the brand ambassador	Do you know ari Lesmana? (participants shown the photo of ari Lesmana)	Yes no
Influencer macro marketing	To identify respondents behavior about the brand ambassador	Do you follow ari lesmana's Instagram account?	Yes No
Brand awareness	To identify respondents behavior about the brand image	Do you know the shoes worn by Ari Lesmana?	Yes (mention the name of the shoes) No
Brand image and influencer marketing	To identify respondents behavior about the correlation between brand image with the influencer marketing	Do you think ari lesmana is the right person to represent the piero?	Scale 1-5
Brand awareness	To identify respondents behavior about the correlation between brand awareness with the influencer marketing	How often do you know other people around you talk about the local brand on the above?	Scale 1-5
Brand awareness	To identify respondents behavior about the correlation between brand awareness with the influencer marketing	When was the last time you saw someone wearing the local shoe brand above?	Scale 1-5
Purchasing decision	To identify respondents behavior about the correlation between brand awareness with the purchasing decision	Have you ever bought the local shoe brand above?	Yes no
Brand image	To identify respondents behavior about the correlation between brand images with trust to the influencer marketing	Have you ever seen influencers on social media wearing the local shoe brands above?	Scale 1-5
Brand image	To identify respondents behavior about the correlation between customers and trust to the brand	For those who have already bought, is the quality of the local shoe brand above in accordance with the price?	Scale 1-5
Brand awareness	To identify respondents behavior about the correlation between brand awareness with brand image	Are you able to recognize the logo of the local shoe brand above well?	Scale 1-5

Brand trust	To identify respondent trust about the shoe brand	How is possibility you recommend the local shoe brand above to friends & family?	Scale 1-5
Brand trust	To identify respondent trust about the shoe brand review by KOL	Do you really trust the shoes reviewed by Macro KOL (Ari lesmana)?	Scale 1-5
Brand trust	To identify respondent trust about the shoe brand review by KOL	Do you really trust that Piero is really suitable with shoes reviewed by Ari lesmana on social media?	Scale 1-5
Purchasing decision	To identify respondent reason buy piero shoes	What is the main reason you decide to buy Piero shoes?	1 = I will not purchase 2 = I trust the shoes review by KOL 3 = I trust that Piero shoes have a good quality 4 = I ever bought Piero shoes so i trust that Piero shoes have a good quality 5 = I trust Piero shoes because Piero shoes has been established since 20 years ago
Purchasing decision	To identify respondent trust and decision to buy product	Do you really trust the shoe review by KOL and decide to buy Piero shoes?	1 = Not trust at all & and not purchase 2 = Not really trust, should see directly 3 = Tentatively 4 = Trust but not directly purchase 5 = Trust and directly will purchase